

Workshop Report on
Enhancing Health and Social Protection Policy
Framework for Migrant Workers in
Kottayam District, Kerala, India
2023

Jointly Organized by

DISHA Foundation Centre of Excellence in Migration & Development
Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB) Project
(CRG/2021/004314),
Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG),
School of International Relations and Politics (SIRP).

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**Workshop Report on
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District, Kerala, India**

2023

One-Day Workshop

**"Enhancing Health and Social Protection Policy
Framework for Migrant Workers in Kottayam
District, Kerala, India"**

2023

REPORT

Date of Workshop : 14th July 2023
Venue : New Seminar Hall,
School of International Relations and Politics,
Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam
Medium of Instruction : English

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Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG),
Second Floor, Room S5
School of International Relations and Politics
Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam -686560
Mail ID: migrationpolicycentre@mgu.ac.in
Phone : +91 8714 77 0906

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Editors

Navas M Khadar

Dr. Bijulal M. V.

Dr Anjali Borhade

Dr Isha Jain

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Navas M Khadar

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Athirampuzha

Kottayam District

Kerala - 686560

Message

In a situation where interstate migrant workers are becoming the main labour force in Kerala, Mahatma Gandhi University's SERB Project (CRG/2021/004314), Disha Foundation, Centre for Migration Policy, and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG), and School of International relations and Politics (SIRP) are jointly conducting a policy formulation workshop. This is part of a continuing exercise for healthcare benefits for interstate migrant workers in Kottayam district. Across India, discussions on policy for interstate migrant workers are maturing at various levels. This workshop brought together Seven Government Departments, Two Government Planning and Policy Institutions, Four Trade Unions, Two NGOs, Three Academic Institutions, Migrant Workers, Researchers and Teachers a focus and action-oriented interactions. Kerala state is discussing the formulation of new law for interstate migrant workers. Recommendations for this conference will provide action-oriented suggestions specifically in the field of health policy, safety and welfare of migrant workers. It is Perhaps, for the first time in Kerala, officials from various departments have come together to hold a discussion for migrant workers. My deep appreciation to *Dr Anjali Borhade* and *Dr Subhojit Dey*, Disha Foundation, for their support. *Dr Bijulal MV* worked tirelessly to make this workshop a success. I take this opportunity to congratulate him and SERB project team. Also, I place on record the support from *Ms Vigneswari IAS*, District collector Kottayam for coordinating with government departments for this programme. I appreciate *Navas M Khadar*, Coordinator of the Kerala workshop, for his dedication and exemplary efforts in making the event a resounding success

I wish the SERB Project, Disha Foundation and Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance will organize such workshops in the future.

Dr C. T. Aravindakumar

Vice Chancellor

Mahatma Gandhi University

Message

I am delighted to congratulate the organisers of the one-day capacity-building organisers on *Enhancing Health and Social Protection Policy Framework for Migrant Workers in Kottayam District, Kerala, India*. The proceedings have immense relevance for the protection, promotion, and dissemination of the right of interstate migrant workers. Economic, social, civil and cultural rights of migrants and the right to life with dignity needs to be protected at social and institutional realms. This is especially true for the interstate migrant worker whose life is filled with various type of vulnerabilities. The impact of remittances on the states of origin of migrant workers and the associated social remittance that migration policies bring in have been substantially highlighted by contemporary research and social interventions in this area.

A substantial share of growth in Kerala has evolved through the participation of interstate migrant workers at different levels of work. According to various estimates, their numbers range between 2 million to 3 million. Developing an environment based on peaceful, non-exploitative work and life conditions will result in a confidence and trust-based environment, ensuring the rights-based guarantees of migrant workers. The SERB Project (CRG/2021/004314), Disha Foundation, Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance, and School of International Relations and Politics intervention to facilitate synergic synchronisation of specific skills and responsibilities by various administrative divisions in the Kottayam district is probably first one of its kind in our country.

I am pleased to be part of this endeavour along with my team of administrators in various departments. I congratulate all of them for their active participation. I also understand that the SERB project has significantly impacted health education and digital literacy relating to migrant workers. The district administration is ready to engage with the SERB project, Disha Foundation, CMPIG-SIRP, independent scholars union leaders, and the media have collaborated in the action related to the areas discussed in this report and the field-level interventions after the workshop.

I extend my warmest congratulations to *Dr C. T. Aravindakumar*, Vice Chancellor of Mahatma Gandhi University, *Dr. Bijulal M. V.*, Principal Investigator of the SERB Project (CRG/2021/004314), *Dr. Anjali Borhade*, Director of Disha Foundation, New Delhi, and the entire team at the Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance, MG University especially the CO-PIs of the SERB project, and Coordinator of the Kerala Workshop for their tireless dedication in organising this workshop and producing this enlightening academic report.

Together, let us continue to strive for the protection of migrant workers' rights and the creation of a more inclusive, equitable, and compassionate society. I wish all the best to the continuing activities and offer my support in field-based interventions.

V. Vigneswari I A S

District Collector
Kottayam

Message

Nearly 28.3% of India's workforce is employed in the informal sector. The jobs in informal sector, is characterized by low paying, insecure jobs and hazardous and exploitative conditions of work. The outbreak of the COVID pandemic in India increased the visibility of migrants and the precarious conditions of their lives and work.

It is realized a multi-sectoral and coordinated policy measures and strategies are vital to deal with the issues of internal migrants, since right to health also includes the underlying social determinants - housing, livelihood, sanitation, work conditions etc. as preconditions of health. Hence, Disha Foundation and World Health Organization, India office under the guidance of NITI Aayog have developed a comprehensive training manual 'Shramik Saarthi' for capacity building of government officials and NGOs to work proactively in the area of migrant health and social determinants. The manual provides practical handholding support to address the many challenges related to labour migration and provide meaningful support to migrant workers, in line with the government's existing program and policy framework in India. The capacity building workshops are being conducted based on 'Shramik Saarthi', a comprehensive training manual to create sustainable support network for migrant workers to address their health and other social determinants of health such as livelihood, legal support, financial inclusion, housing and education.

In this regard, I would like to express my special thanks to the *Dr C. T. Aravindakumar* Vice Chancellor, and *Dr Bijulal M. V.* and the entire *SERB Project team* at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam for providing a platform to organise successful workshop in Kottayam. It was heartening to see collaboration of District collector and Mahatma Gandhi University for such an important initiative. I sincerely thank the district collector *Smt. V. Vigheshwari* for her wholehearted support and participation in this workshop. I thank all the government officials, NGOs and trade unions for their enthusiastic participation in the workshop. Their assurance to work on migrant's specific health and social protection plan, which may be incorporated in district action plan of Kottayam is also very encouraging and innovative.

My best wishes to all the stakeholders for continuous engagement in this regard!

Dr Anjali Borhade

Director

DISHA Foundation Centre of Excellence in Migration & Development

Message

According to the United Nations' 2020 global estimate, there are approximately 281 million international migrants (IOM 2022). This equates to 3.6 per cent of the global population. Migration progress are progressing beyond definitions. According to the 2011 census, the number of internal migrants (both inter-state and intra-state) in India is 45.36 crore, which is 37% of the country's population. Figures from states such as Goa, Delhi, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Karnataka reflect the country's total internal migration (Economic Survey 2017). The all-India migration rate from July 2020 to June 2021 was 28.9%. The rate is 26.5% in rural areas and 34.9% in urban areas (Migration in India Report 2021). In this context, there is a need to discuss inter-state migration in Kerala more seriously.

For the SERB Project, data accessed through the right to information from the Kerala Labor Department for the SERB Project says there are 516,320 migrant workers in Kerala (SERB RTI, 2023). However, the estimates of the Kerala Planning Board Report in 2021, place it between 28 lakh to 34 lakh. Fieldwork in the SERB Project has shown that beyond. The mismatch in numbers, migrant workers in Kerala are vulnerable to unhealthy and insecure socio-economic situations. But migrant workers prefer to work in Kerala because they get more human rights guarantees than many other states, and in terms of wages, Kerala provides higher wages than other states in India.

The Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG), which does substantive policy support work for migrant workers, has come out with evidence of a considerable lack of digital literacy among migrant workers. Transitions to digital facilities has redefined social modes of communication where migrant workers are heavily marginalised and exploited. The SERB-MGU workshop, jointly organised by the DISHA Foundation and CMPIG which has done comprehensive attention to the

issues of migrant workers in Kerala, can be seen as the second intervention in the country, the first one begins conducted by NITI Aayog in 2020. The SERB project organized such a workshop by bringing together various government departments in the Kottayam district of Kerala.

The Draft National Migrant Labor Policy prepared by NITI Aayog 2020 has not yet reached completion. Incidentally, the Kerala government trying to bring a new law for inter-state migrant workers in Kerala. The SERB project team believes that this workshop's recommendations will motivate the government to conduct similar workshops in other districts of Kerala and that the recommendations will be discussed at the government level.

Prof. C. T. Aravindakumar, the Vice Chancellor of Mahatma Gandhi University, extended comprehensive support for the workshop. *District Collector V. Vigneshwari I A S*, who efficiently coordinated various departments in Kottayam district, *Dr. Anjali Borhade*, and the *Disha Foundation*, offered crucial financial backing for the workshop's success. *Navas M. Khadar*, the Coordinator of the Kerala Workshop, played a pivotal role in ensuring its success. *Dr. Subhojit Dey*, Executive Director of the Disha Foundation, made a significant contribution to the academic session. Thank SIRP Director *Prof. C. Vinodan*, SERB co-investigators, student coordinators, and all other participants and representatives involved. Our heartfelt gratitude is offered to all of those who have supported our workshop and contributed to its success.

Bijulal M. V.

Principal Investigator

Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB) Project (CRG/2021/004314),

&

Chairperson

Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG)

Forward

Internal migration has emerged as a dominant source of the labour force in Kerala. A collaborative effort was undertaken by the SERB Project, Disha Foundation, Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance of the School of International Relations and Politics, and Mahatma Gandhi University to review the migration situation from an inclusive governance perspective. Together, these organizations orchestrated a one-day workshop titled "Enhancing the Health and Social Protection Policy Framework for Migrant Workers in Kottayam District, Kerala, India." To facilitate a cross-sectoral dialogue to identify and address the most relevant issues about protecting migrant's rights.

The workshop drew participation from a diverse group, including Migrant Workers, the Labor Department, the Health Department, the Medical College Department, the Women and Child Department, the Community Medicine Department, NGOs, the District Planning Board, the Local Self-Governing Department, Trade Unions, Teachers, Researchers, and Independent Scholars. In total, 40 individuals took part in the one-day event. Dr. Bijulal MV, Principal Investigator of the SERB Project, and Dr. Anjali Borhade, Director of the Disha Foundation, skillfully moderated the sessions.

Throughout the workshop, various departments conducted interactive sessions, leading to a significant revelation: the challenges faced by migrant workers could only be effectively addressed through coordinated efforts across different departments. This event marked a pioneering initiative in Kerala, setting a precedent for the entire nation and spanning a year-long engagement.

The success of the SERB-DISHA-CMPIG-SIRP workshop was possible only through the contributions and support of several individuals and organizations. Special thanks were extended to Prof. C.T. Aravindakumar, Vice-Chancellor of Mahatma Gandhi University, whose insightful suggestions significantly contributed to the

workshop's success. District Collector V. Vigneswari IAS played pivotal role in coordinating various departments' efforts to ensure the workshop's successful completion. Additionally, the Disha Foundation, under the leadership of Dr. Anjali Borhade, provided crucial financial support.

Acknowledgement is also due to Dr Bijulal M.V, Chairperson of the Center for Migration Policy and Inclusive Research, who served as the Principal Investigator for the SERB Project, and Dr. C. Vinodhan, Director of the School of International Relations and Politics, Dr Subhojit Dey, Executive Director Disha Foundation, Dr Isha Jain, Programme coordinator, Disha Foundation as well as the dedicated student coordinators who worked tirelessly to make the workshop a success.

This report comes out in the context of the state government's discussions for an updated policy for migrant workers in Kerala. The workshop has produced a comprehensive report containing recommendations for initiating conversations on a new interstate migrant law. The report provides valuable insights and guidance on measures that the government should consider in formulating policies to protect the rights and ensure welfare of migrant workers. Based on these recommendations, the state of Kerala could develop a migrant-friendly legal framework that includes social, cultural, health and occupational rights. In this endeavour, similar workshops should be conducted in all 14 districts of Kerala, and their insights should be coordinated for legislation.

Navas M. Khadar

Workshop Coordinator

&

Project Associate

Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB) Project (CRG/2021/004314)

Organization Team

Ms. V. Vigneswari I A S, District Collector, Kottayam

Dr Bijulal M. V., Principal Investigator, SERB Project.

Dr C T Aravindakumar, Vice Chancellor, Mahatma Gandhi University.

Dr Anjali Borhade, Director Disha Foundation.

Dr Subhojit Dey, Executive Director, Disha Foundation.

Dr. Isha Jain, Program Manager, Disha Foundation.

Dr P P Noushad, Co-Investigator, SERB Project.

Dr Abdul Jabbar, Co-Investigator, SERB Project.

Dr Rajesh Many, Co-Investigator, SERB Project.

Mr. Navas M. Khadar, Workshop Coordinator, Kerala.

Coordinating Team

Ms. Anjusha A.

Ms. Devi chandana. M.

MS. Haripriya Sathyarajan

Mr. Jaison Thomas

Mr. Jose Deepak T. T.

Ms. Nadia K. Joseph

Mr. Said Muhammad Sadat

Mr. Sambhunarayan A. S.

Ms. Sneha A. S.

Ms. Sreya S

Contents

SI No	Title	Page No:
1	Executive Summary	1
2	About the Organizers	3
3	About the Workshop	5
4	Workshop Participants	6
5	Inaugural Session	8
6	Viewpoint of Kottayam District Collector	10
7	Insights from Dr C Vinodan	12
8	SERB Activity Report: Dr P.P Noushad	13
9	Ice-Breaking Session	15
10	Dr Anjali Borhade Presentations	19
11	Dr Bijulal M. V., Presentation	21
12	Group Discussion	25
13	Outcome of the Workshop	32
14	Appendix - Conference Photos	36

Executive Summary

This one day workshop on “Enhancing Health and Social Protection Policy Framework for Migrant Workers in Kottayam District, Kerala, India” was recognized in partnership with the Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), Disha Foundation, and the Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance of the School of International Relations and Politics at M.G. University. The goals of the one-day workshop were, (1) to give a functional introduction to the training manual “*Shramik Saarthi*” by Disha Foundation (2) to discuss the research finding of the SERB project (3) to introduce the idea of inclusive governance and human right audit of welfare practices prepared by the CMPIG. The workshop was held on 14 July 2023 at the School of International Relations and Politics New Seminar Hall.

This workshop specifically focused on the pressing health and social protection issues faced by interstate migrant workers in the region. Disha Foundation, a well-known non-profit recognizing supporting recognizing groups such as migrant and unorganized workers, played a crucial role in co-organising the event. This programme was the offshoot of the University’s partnership with the Department of Science and Technology (DST) of the Government of India in the SERB project titled “Effect of Social, Institutional and Technological Interventions to Access to Healthcare Among Interstate Migrant Labourers in Kerala” (CRG 2021/004314), launched in September 2022. The workshop brought together various stakeholders, including representatives from the state’s migrant communities, government officials, medical experts, researchers, trade unionists, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs).

This cooperative effort was made in the Kottayam District to improve migrant workers’ access to social and health protection. The workshop provided a forum for stimulating conversations, knowledge exchange, and developing workable initiatives. Participants were aware of the challenges faced by interstate migrant workers. The key objective was to enhance policies and frameworks to successfully address the issues and assure the welfare of interstate migrant workers.

The joint participation of numerous government agencies, including the Departments of health, public policy, labour, planning board, women and child, LSGD, community medicine, de-addiction, KILA state’s planning institute, and KILE state labour institute

the demonstrated a concerted effort to coordinate policies and prioritise resources for the safety of migrant workers. A crucial part of the discussions was also played by committed labour and employment organisations, who conveyed their recognizing knowledge to create inclusive plans and solve this disadvantaged group's difficulties. Through comprehensive solutions, this concentrated effort attempted to protect the welfare and promote the constitutional and human rights of migrant workers.

In addition, to this the workshop actively benefited though the attendance by healthcare professionals from various backgrounds, including physicians and medical staff from several departments. It was evident that their depth of knowledge and practical experience in addressing the health issues of migrant workers would improve their discussions and help formulate suggestions based on reliable data. The event was successive to promote informed and practical ideas for enhancing the well-being of migrant workers by embracing their priceless insights.

The workshop ensured that workers' organisations' voices and perspectives were adequately represented by engaging trade union officials. The workshop additionally aimed to tap into the recognizing knowledge of researchers and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) working on migration-related issues by actively incorporating them in policy lobbying and advocating inclusive development. By recognizing these stakeholders' expertise and fostering significant change in migrant worker rights and well-being. The workshop was successful to create benchmarks for collaborative actions for rights protection.

Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance, SIRP M G University gave different parties a platform to work together, exchange knowledge, and develop workable solutions. The workshop aimed to preserve interstate migrant workers' rights, well-being, and equitable access to high-quality medical care and social protection by concentrating on their pressing concerns. This inclusive and highly interactive programme showed a determined effort to address the vulnerable community's unique needs and difficulties, promoting a more accountable and inclusive environment.

About The Organizers:

1. Disha Foundation Centre of Excellence in Migration & Development

Disha Foundation Centre of Excellence in Migration & Development has been working since 2002 to empower tribal and other migrant communities and low economic groups in India through capacity building, livelihood training, and leadership development. Disha has set up MRC (Migration Research and Resource Centre) to cater to the health and social protection needs of the migrants. Disha Foundation has been recognised as a National Centre of Excellence in Migration, Health, and Development by the Ministry of Tribal Affairs (MoTA). Also, Disha was a member of the NITI Aayog sub-committee for migrant workers for their inclusion in national policies. The World Health Organization, India office and Disha Foundation, Centre of Excellence in Migration & Development, under the guidance of NITI Aayog, have developed a comprehensive training manual (Shramik Saarthi) for capacity building of government officials and civil society organisations to create a sustainable support network for migrant workers to address their health, livelihood, legal support.

2. Science and Engineering Research Board Project (CRG/2021/004314).

The project entitled *“Effect of Social Institutional and Technological Interventions on Access to Healthcare Among Inter-State Migrant Labourers In Kerala”* proposed Interstate Migrant Workers’ Access to Healthcare Information System (IMWATHIS) is envisioned to develop a multidimensional information dissemination mechanism based on Baseline Studies, Randomized Controlled Trials, Data Analysis and Systematic Research to enhance policy responses in the field of public health services for interstate migrant workers in India. The IMWATHIS would initially be tested in the social sites in Kerala, India’s leading pro-migrant policy-making state, to replicate the same in other states. The lack of data on crucial policy measures for tangible and time-bound outcomes is evident in the Indian context. Although the migrant labour force contributes significantly to the country’s development, significant social

indicators of migrant workers are unavailable due to the severe shortage of reliable updated data. The proposed IMWATHIS is intended as a single access point to the best available public health data and information to support contemporary migration policy discourse and decision-making in line with the WHO standards and other international standard, including the GCM, inputs from internationally accepted studies.

3. Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG)

The Centre for Migration and Policy Inclusive Governance (CMPIG) is a centre for academic research devoted to all international national and local migration aspects. The centre advances new thinking of migration is one of the significant hubs of interdisciplinary research networks and promote a new nexus of international migration experts. The centre creates a platform for debate, research, policy analysis, and community engagement on global, national, and local scales. The CMPIG will collaborate with government and non-government organisations that deal with refugees, international migrants, and migrant workers in the region. The CMPIG, with its distinguished scholar network, will work to develop a new thematic pathway and facilitate future scholars to disseminate knowledge through academic publications, create thematic data banks, training programs on field activities, and conferences.

4. School of International Relations and Politics (SIRP)

The SIRP was established as one of the founding academic departments of Mahatma Gandhi University on 2 October 1983. From its modest beginnings, the school has, over four decades, acquired for itself a solid and enviable reputation. It has made a mark in its sphere of scholarly activity. It is one of the few institutions in the country to offer instruction and research in politics, international relations, human rights, public policy, and governance. In the filed of social research SIRP has been consistently active. Social lab programme is a significant addition in its extension activities to understand communities through collaborative engagements.

About the Workshop

The World Health Organization, India office and Disha Foundation, Centre of Excellence in Migration & Development, under the guidance of NITI Aayog, have developed a comprehensive training manual (Shramik Saarthi) for capacity building of government officials and civil society organisations to create a sustainable support network for interstate migrant workers and to address their health, livelihood, legal support, financial inclusion, housing and education issues.

In this regard, Disha Foundation, Science and Engineering Research Board Project (CRG/2021/004314), Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance, School of International Relations and Politics Mahatma Gandhi University Kottayam has conducted Capacity Building Workshop On ***“Enhancing Health and Social Protection Policy Framework for Migrant Workers in Kottayam District, Kerala, India”*** at New Seminar Hall, School of International Relations and Politics for Government officials, Trade Union Workers, Interstate Migrant Workers, Researchers, and NGOs at Kottayam district, Kerala, India.

The program had a presentation on the countrywide experiments followed by a detailed discussion on the possibilities of developing a policy framework and methodology for inclusive policy to have an inclusive and comprehensive program in the specific area of healthcare and access to healthcare.

The key objectives of the training workshops were:

1. Develop draft points for ‘Migrant’s Health and Social Protection Plan’ for Kottayam district.
2. Form a group of trainers capable of imparting their learnings to a broader audience, both government official and NGOs/trade unions.
3. To assist government officials and civil society organisations in developing their understanding of various issues of migrant workers.
4. To provide the patterns with handholding/assistance in developing and implementing research and interventions for migrants on various issues in their respective geographies.
5. To provide detailed insights about the government’s various existing schemes and policies for workers in recognizing sectors and migrant workers.
6. Developing strategies for targeted inclusion of migrant workers in existing programs and plan how best government departments and NGOs may collaborate for its successful implementation.

Participants List

	Name	Designation	Institution	Phone Number	Email
1	Adv Binu Bose	Gen Secretary	Migrant Workers Union Kerala / AITUC	+91 86065 54137	advbinub@gmail.com
2	Adv Sheeja Anil	District Secretary,	CITU	+91 94473 48293	sheejaanil@gmail.com
3	Ambareesh T S	Research Scholar	Mahatma Gandhi University	+91 9947457753	ambareesh@gmail.com
4	Aniyan Mathew	State Vice President	INTUC	+91 94476 01656	aniyanmathew81@gmail.com
5	Arun B.R	Research Associate	Kerala Labour and Employment (KILE)	+91 9495563436	abr26@yahoo.com
6	Aswin Rajan Varghese	Research Scholar	SIRP	+91 98844 89543	aswinrajan@mgu.ac.in
7	Athitha Sunil	Research Scholar	SIRP	+91 99954 64596	athithasunil@gmail.com
8	Binuraj K.S	Faculty	Kerala Institute of Local Administration	+91 90616 70397	binurajks@kila.ac.in
9	Domy John	District Education Media Officer, Kottayam	Health Department	+91 70120 43489	demokottayam@gmail.com
10	Dr Ajith Thomas Mathew	Medical Officer, PHC Payippad	Health Department	+91 8606212769	payippadgp@gmail.com
11	Dr Amurthraj R.M	Thematic Expert (LSDGs)	Kerala Institute of Local Administration	+91 894300 4093	amurthraj@kila.ac.in
12	Dr Biju George	Associate Professor	Medical College, Kottayam	+91 9846100093	bijugeorge1@gmail.com
13	Dr Binoy A.A	Researcher	Independent Researcher	+91 99474 15435	binoya@gmail.com
14	Dr M Rafeeka Beevi	Research Officer	Kerala Institute of Labour and Employment	+91 89436 70899	researchkile@gmail.com
15	Dr Mathew A Varghese	Chairperson	Centre for Urban Studies, SIRP	+91 94462 17402	aluvaperiyar@gmail.com
16	Dr Nancy Liza Thomas	ICDS Supervisor	Women and Child Department	+91 9809678911	nanacymoolhu1053@gmail.com
17	Dr S. Anil Kumar	Medical Officer, PHC Athirampuzha	Health Department	+91 7559905335	athirampuzhagp@gmail.com
18	Dr Sairu Philip	HoD Community Medicine, Kottayam	Kottayam Medical College	+91 99615 39802	Siaruphilip2018@gmail.com
19	Dr Santhosh	Lecturer	Community Medicine, Kottayam	+91 9074713353	santhoshkumarag@gmail.com
20	Dr Silpa Satheesh	Sociologist	School of Social Science	+91 6282188 113	silpasatheesh@mgu.ac.in

21	Dr Sreejith K. K	Medical Officer	Vimukthi De Addiction Centre, Govt. General Hospital Pala	+91 89210 89789	vimukthikottayam@gmail.com
22	Dr Vidyadharan P N	Deputy District Medical Office, Kottayam	Health Department	+91 94474 44061	drvidyadharan@gmail.com
23	Dr. Abdul Jabbar	Co-Investigator	SERB project, MGU	+91 7907210172	abdul@mgu.ac.in
24	George Mathew	Director	Progressive Workers Organisation	+91 94473 01567	progressiveworkersorganisation@gmail.com
27	Jais Joseph	Accountat	Grama Panchayath, Erumeli	+91 9495684242	erumeligpkm@gmail.com
25	Jayasree M	District Labour Officer, Kottayam	Labour Department	+91 94474 70186	dlokottayam@gmail.com
26	Jerin P.C	Research Scholar	School of Pedagogical Science, MGU	+91 886728349	jerintykattupapappalli@gmail.com
28	Libin K Kuriakose	District Project Manager	Labour Department	+91 9496007105	libinmsw@gmail.com
29	Litty Mathew	District Planning Officer, Kottayam	District Planning Board	+91 94460 94381	dpokottayam@gmail.com
30	Nikhil John	School of Computer Science MGU, Rajasthan Native	Student from Mahatma Gandhi University	+91 97478 63850	mr.nikhiljohn@gmail.com
31	Pramod Kumar Bharti	Migrant Worker	Bihar	+91 7306818697	pramodkumarb@gmail.com
32	Prof V Mathew Kurian	Joint Director	KN Raj study centre for Planning and centre-state financial relations	+91 94970 89219	kurienvazhachira@gmail.com
33	Prof. P.P Noushad	Co-Investigator	SERB project, MGU	+91 9447675755	noushadmgu@gmail.com
34	R Rajendran	District Joint Secretary	BMS	+91 98466 22855	rajendranpandalam@gmail.com
35	Rasheeda V.P	Supervisor	Women and Child Department	+91 9447689924	rashee.msw@gmail.com
37	Shanil Bright S P	Representative	Grama Panchayath, Kanjirappaly	+91 91 8075156646	kanjirappalygp@gmail.com
38	Sunil Kumar B	JHI	FHC, Payippad	+91 8075718600	sunilanchalummoodu@gmail.com
37	T.G Sathyapal	Rtd Officer	Kerala Civil Supplies Department.	+91 94472 88896	Sathyapal1967@gmail.com
39	Thresiamma Mathew	Director	Archana Women Centre	+91 94473 51806	Thresiamma.ommi@gmail.com
40	Vineed S	Assistant Labour Officer	Labour Department	+91 9447704348	kottayamalo@gmail.com

INAUGURAL SESSION

Summary

The School of International Relations and Politics at M.G. University successfully organised a workshop titled “Enhancing the Health and Social Protection Policy Framework for Migrant Workers in Kottayam District.” This collaborative event was jointly conducted with Disha Foundation, Science and Engineering Research Board Project and the Centre for Migration Policy and Inclusive Governance (CMPIG), SIRP, M.G. University. The workshop aimed to address the challenges faced by migrant workers and develop effective policies to meet their needs. Dr MV Bijulal, the Principal Investigator of SERB MG University and Chairperson of CMPIG, served as the key organiser for the programmes. Ms V. Vigneshwari IAS, the Kottayam District Collector, emphasised the workshop’s significance as a starting point for addressing migrant worker challenges at an academic level. Ms V. Vigneshwari stressed the need to reassess existing government activities and consider the well-being of migrant workers beyond just health

concerns. Ms Vigneshwari also encouraged participants to study the problems in a global perspective while dealing with migrant workers, particularly regarding social protection and education. The workshop commenced with a context-setting speech by Dr Anjali Borhade, the director of the Disha Foundation, who ensured that the event had a meaningful purpose and clear direction.

Prof. Aravindakumar, Vice-chancellor, Mahatma Gandhi University highlighted the importance of understanding the baseline knowledge about migrant workers and acknowledged the paradigm shift in Kerala's approach towards them. He expressed confidence in the data collected from the workshop's delegates, believing it would significantly contribute to future policy-making endeavours. Prof. C Vinodan, the Director of the School of International Relations and Politics, and Adv. Reji Zacharia, member of the M.G. University syndicate, delivered felicitation speeches. Dr Anjali Borhade, the Director of the Disha Foundation, handled the pivotal session of the workshop, providing comprehensive insights and context for meaningful discussions and subsequent policy enhancements. The workshop agenda focused on improving health and social protection policies for migrant workers. The discussions were aimed to provide valuable insights and set the stage for in-depth deliberations. A diverse group of 40 participants from civil, administrative, academic, and migrant representatives participated, fostering a comprehensive understanding of federal policy-making mechanisms

The symbiotic link between migrants and the state guarantees Kerala's sustained growth and development: Kottayam District Collector V. Vigneshwari

Kerala, a state in India, offers significant opportunities for migrants, in the opinion of Collector Vigneshwari, due to its relatively higher wage rates and opportunities in the market for labour intensive jobs caused by migration of Kerala residents to other areas. It is

essential to recognize that migrant workers contribute significantly to Kerala's growth and that their employment depends not just on the state's goodwill. In fact, these dedicated migrant workers' significant contributions are a major part of Kerala's economy.

In addition, Ms Vigneshwari said that while we recognize the value of migrant labour, we also see that hiring them is a mutually advantageous agreement rather than solely an act of kindness or favors. In Kerala, migrants support the economy and meet the labour shortage, and the state also offers job opportunities that draw migrants due to better earnings. The symbiotic link between migrants and the state guarantees Kerala's sustained growth and development.

When their family are not with them, migrants, particularly women, experience severe socio-psychological difficulties. Feelings of loneliness, homesickness, and emotional anguish can arise when separated from their loved ones. Migrants frequently hope

for a brighter future, but Ms Vigneshwari noted that their progress may be hindered due to emotional hindrance and may impact their general well-being.

Ms Vigneshwari also raised the problem of migrant employees receiving unequal pay for equivalent work. It is unfair that certain migrant workers receive less wage for their labour than Malayalee workers. As they are not fairly compensated for their work, this wage disparity can contribute to the feeling that they are treated as second-class people.

Adopting an optimistic approach is vital as we address the challenges faced by migrants and work towards an inclusive society. Effective communication fosters understanding and empathy between the native population and migrants. Kerala's need for additional labour is undeniable, and the presence of migrant workers has been a great help in fulfilling this requirement. Recognising and appreciating their contribution to the state's development is essential.

As Kerala experiences the influx of migrant workers, it presents a unique opportunity to set a positive precedent for treating these individuals. Treating workers with dignity, respect, and fair wages benefits them and lays the foundation for more harmonious coexistence in the future.

Doing so, ensures that coming generations of migrant workers will feel welcomed and valued, fostering a culture of inclusive growth and progression.

It is crucial to avoid "othering" and prevent the creation of a second-class citizen. Embracing the diversity that migrants bring enriches the cultural tapestry of Kerala and strengthens the state's social fabric. Key areas of engagement, inclusivity, and fair treatment will be key drivers in building a unified community where all members, regardless of their background, can thrive and contribute positively to society.

Taking proactive steps to address the concerns and aspirations of migrant workers will help prevent cultural repercussions like the anti-migrant movements witnessed in some Western countries. By recognizing the value that workers bring to the state and ensuring their integration into the social and economic landscape, we can promote a more tolerant and compassionate society.

Advancing Dignity and Inclusive Governance

(Insights from Prof. C Vinodan's Migration Study and the Vision for the Kottayam Model)

Prof. C Vinodan highlighted the security concerns of the native population, social exclusion faced by migrants, and human rights violations. Notably, the right to dignity, enshrined as a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Indian constitution, gained significant attention in the discussion. Protecting the dignity of all individuals, including migrants, is of utmost importance in ensuring a just and inclusive society.

Drawing inspiration from the current initiatives, Prof. Vinodan expressed hope for developing a Kottayam model of inclusive governance. This model aims to address the challenges faced by migrants and create a framework that promotes their rights, welfare, and overall well-being. By fostering inclusive governance practices, Kottayam can set an example for other regions to follow, paving the way for a more harmonious and equitable society where the rights and dignity of every individual are respected and upheld. Dr Vinodan congratulated the efforts by center for migration policy and inclusive governance.

Empowering Migrant Workers: The SERB Project's Impact and the Promising Path Forward

(Talk by Prof. P.P Noushad)

In September 2022, the wheels of the SERB project were set into motion, marking a significant step towards addressing the welfare and health rights of migrant workers in Kerala. Embarking on an ambitious journey, the SERB team-initiated fieldwork across 12 districts of Kerala, delving into the lives of migrant workers and directly engaging

with them. As this endeavour unfolds, the spotlight is turning to the Kottayam policy workshop, poised to emerge as a significant outcome of the SERB project.

The SERB project, propelled by a dedication to support, empower, and rebuild the

lives of migrant workers, has swiftly gained momentum since its inception. A notable aspect of this endeavour is the collaboration with the Disha Foundation. This entity has played a key role in shaping health policies tailored for the migrant workforce in India. This partnership signifies a convergence of purpose, combining grassroots efforts with systemic change, ultimately fostering a more equitable environment for those who contribute significantly to our nation's growth.

A vital stride towards the betterment of migrant workers' lives lies in policy formulation. These workshops serve as a crucible of ideas, where stakeholders from different domains congregate to shape health policies that cater specifically to the unique challenges faced by migrant workers. It's an endeavour that aims not just to bridge the gaps in healthcare accessibility but also to reiterate society's commitment towards inclusivity.

A striking testament to the power of collaboration, this discourse is gaining prominence as a beacon of hope amidst discussions about migrant worker policies in

Kerala. The Kottayam District Collector Ms V Vigneswari unwavering support has proved instrumental in orchestrating this groundbreaking workshop, marking the first time that departments have come together in an integrated manner. The fusion of perspectives and expertise is poised to yield innovative solutions that can shape policies within Kottayam and reverberate throughout the state and beyond.

In the broader context of Kerala, a state that has often led the way in socio-economic and human development indices, the outcomes of the Kerala workshop hold immense significance. The workshop's outcomes will undoubtedly

be scrutinised, discussed, and eventually integrated into the tapestry of policies that determine the trajectory of migrant workers' lives. This concerted effort to provide a conducive environment for migrant workers is particularly timely as Kerala grapples with the multifaceted challenges posed by migration.

As the SERB project advances, as minds converge in the Kottayam policy debate, and as the narratives of migrant workers begin to intertwine with policy frameworks, a new chapter is being penned in the annals of India's socio-economic landscape. The efforts to support, empower, and rebuild the lives of migrant workers are not mere words but tangible actions that herald a brighter, more inclusive future. Through collaborative policy formulation, compassionate governance, and a steadfast commitment to the welfare of every individual, regardless of their origins, the journey towards a fairer and more equitable society gains momentum. And it all begins with projects like SERB and platforms like the Kerala workshop - where dreams are intertwined with policies and aspirations are given a voice.

Context Setting

Strengthening Collaboration among Government and Trade Unions/ NGOs for Migrant Welfare and Labor Rights in Kerala:

Dr. Anjali Borhade

Dr Anjali Borhade started her speech with a sense of excitement and vigour. She stressed that to ensure that Kerala's exceptional growth continues to benefit everyone, including the migrants, addressing the rights and welfare of migrants requires a collective effort involving trade unions and non-governmental organisations (NGOs).

According to a 2017 study, Kerala is a popular place for migrants to settle because of its higher minimum wages and an array of assistance programmes, including the government's welfare kit and health insurance programme "Aawaz." Despite these advancements, it is essential to acknowledge that migrants

are not fully aware about these schemes hence face exclusion after arriving in Kerala.

Dr Anjali Borhade stressed the necessity of strengthening NGOs and unions to address these issues and ensure the welfare of migrants. Trade unions are essential in protecting the rights of employees, especially immigrants, and promoting just compensation, secure working conditions, and anti-exploitation measures. Migrants can benefit more from the state's welfare programmes and become more aware of their rights by working with trade unions.

Additionally, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) are crucial in helping migrants. These organisations can facilitate migrant's and their families' access to essential services, including psychotherapy, legal support, healthcare, and education. Trade unions and NGOs can collaborate with respective government departments to build a robust support system that solves the numerous difficulties faced by migrants in Kerala.

The Ice-Breaking Session

The icebreaking session aimed to foster understanding among participants by exploring the perspectives of migrant workers through a creative activity that highlighted the uniqueness of individuals while emphasizing the aspirations and rights of these workers in society.

Session Overview:

The icebreaking session commenced with an introduction to the importance of understanding for different societal roles, particularly those of migrant workers. A total of 40 participants took part in the activity. Each participant was handed a self-declaration paper on which they were instructed to write various details about themselves as if they were a migrant worker.

The details included:

- Age.
- Marital Status.
- Who is the most important person in your life?
- What makes you happy (20 words)
- What is your biggest fear? (20 words)
- What is your favourite festival?
- Your favourite Bollywood actor
- If you were given all the money that you wanted and the freedom to spend it in any manner,
- what would you do with it?

Activity Execution:

After completing their self-declaration papers, all the sheets were collected and shuffled into a box. This anonymized mixing ensured that participants' responses were disconnected from their identities. Next, a participant was invited to approach the box, select a paper, and read aloud the details provided on it.

Revelation and Reflection:

As the selected participant read the details aloud, an interesting dynamic unfolded. Whenever the reader's details matched those written on a sheet, the participant who authored that sheet would stand up and acknowledge that it was their own. This led to moments of surprise, laughter, and even introspection, as participants realized the commonalities and unique qualities they shared with their peers.

Key Takeaways:

1. **Diversity in Aspirations:** The session vividly illustrated that everyone, regardless of their background, has distinct aspirations and dreams. This reinforced the idea that migrant workers, often overlooked or misunderstood, also possess their own ambitions and goals.
2. **Shared Experiences:** Through the activity, participants recognized shared interests and experiences, fostering connections and empathy among them. This highlighted the importance of understanding and appreciating diverse perspectives.
3. **Rights:** By focusing on migrant workers' aspirations, the session subtly conveyed the message that everyone, regardless of their role in society, deserves rights, respect, and understanding.

The icebreaking session effectively achieved its objectives by engaging participants in an interactive activity that humanized the experiences of migrant workers. The session not only showcased the uniqueness of individuals but also highlighted the shared desires and rights that transcend societal roles. It left participants with a deeper appreciation for diversity and a stronger commitment to inclusion.

Presentation – I Dr Anjali's Insights and Debunked Myths

Dr Anjali Borhade

Dr Anjali's study made several important deductions, one of which was the importance of remittances in areas like Bihar, where many households greatly rely on the money sent home by their migrant relatives. This fact emphasises how crucial it is to solve the problems faced by migrant workers and ensure their well-being, both for

their own sake and for the continued economic health of their home regions.

The study also clarified the pull and push variables influencing migration, notably from areas like Rajasthan, Bihar, and Uttar Pradesh. Understanding these elements is crucial for creating targeted support programmes that tackle the underlying reasons for migration and improve chances for residents.

Dr Anjali highlighted the prevalence of several myths surrounding migrant workers, including the misconception that they are vectors of diseases. However, she highlighted the necessity of dispelling these myths and emphasised that only people in good condition would go on such an arduous journey. Instead of pre-existing health conditions, migrants frequently develop poor health conditions because of their demanding working settings. The general health and well-being of migrants can be significantly enhanced by addressing these work-related problems and guaranteeing better working circumstances.

Furthermore, Dr Anjali Borhade underscored the importance of not burdening the health system with the responsibility of addressing migrant-related issues. Treating migrants as burdens is neither a justification nor a solution to their challenges. Instead, she advocated for a proactive approach that involves providing appropriate

healthcare and social support to migrants, just like any other group in society.

The study further sheds light on the significant challenges posed by poor maternal, reproductive, social, and mental health

conditions experienced by migrants. Urgent attention and intervention are essential to ensure equitable access to healthcare for this vulnerable population, contributing to their overall well-being. By conducting and disseminating this research, we aim to raise awareness and foster a more inclusive and empathetic society that recognizes the struggles faced by migrants. Addressing these pressing issues will lead to a more comprehensive approach to policymaking, better support systems, and improved living conditions for migrants in Kerala and beyond. We must work together to create positive change and promote the rights and welfare of all individuals in our society.

Presentation - II

Understanding the Dynamics of Migration and its Impact

Dr. Bijulal M. V.

The SERB initiative, which aims to promote a more inclusive approach to connecting with migrant citizens in the policy and governmental sectors without discrimination,

was extended in an exciting presentation by Dr M.V. Bijulal. His emphasis on migration brought home that it is frequently pursued in search of better living conditions and is not just a transient transfer. He discussed

citizenship during the talk, highlighting the distinction between official and actual citizenships as illustrated by the social and political experiences of migrant workers.

The use of terminology like "Madarasi" and "Bengali" to denote the 'other' or the second-class status assigned to individuals was one crucial issue brought up by Dr Bijulal. These terms contribute to the marginalisation of immigrant groups by fostering xenophobia like situations and intolerance. He encouraged the audience to consider how such opperssive categorization can obstruct genuine inclusivity and prevent all people from experiencing faithful citizenship.

Dr Bijulal stressed the obligation that Indian citizens have to one another under the constitution and prompted audience members to consider their contributions to advancing a just and equitable society. He encouraged everyone to reflect on whether their actions have honoured the values entrenched in the constitution that safeguard fairness for everyone, and he urged for aserious self-examination.

The presentation emphasised the necessity of a paradigm shift in how society perceives and handles migrant workers—accepting them as important contributors to

the country's development rather than viewing them as "others" or second-class citizens is critical. By doing this, policymakers and the government may foster an atmosphere in which prejudice is eradicated, and everyone is treated with respect and dignity, regardless of their nationality or position as an immigrant.

The audience responded favourably to Dr Bijul's appeal for reflection and self-examination, which led people to consider their deeds and attitudes towards other citizens. He emphasised how crucial it is to understand that creating an inclusive society that supports the values of justice

and equality for everyone is a shared duty. The presentation also stressed how important it is for the government and policymakers to support a culture that values diversity and recognises the contributions of all people, especially immigrants. The government may foster social integration possibilities and create an environment where immigrants can prosper and advance the country by implementing inclusive policies and practices.

Another vital feature of migration that was not previously discussed was the notion of invisibility. Dr M. V. Bijul stressed how, as members of the labour force, we sometimes overlook those people who devote their entire life to a particular of work life. Some people must work to survive, while others may choose to do so to support themselves. Particularly in an urban setting, people can blend into the background in search of anonymity amid busy daily life.

This paradoxical invisibility has advantages and disadvantages. On the one hand, it grants people a certain amount of freedom and anonymity, enabling them to move

about city life unobserved. On the other hand, this invisibility can result in rights violations and worker abuse. Migrant workers may be more susceptible to unfair treatment and exploitation by dishonest employers without solid links with other employees or the

lack of knowledge of current labour laws and regulations.

The lack of visibility also extends to society's perception of migrant workers. Their problems are frequently ignored or underestimated, and their contributions are commonly neglected. This increases the obstacles faced by migrant workers and feeds a cycle of marginalisation. To address this issue, it is crucial to build an atmosphere that promotes the visibility and appreciation of every member of the labour force, regardless of their background or line of work. Creating solid bonds among employees can help them stand up for their rights and receive fair treatment because of their combined power and empowerment. Additionally, migrant workers may be empowered to demand better working conditions and protection from exploitation if they are aware of labour laws and their rights. Recent worker's struggle against wage denials and wage theft are showing the increases of unity among workers.

To ensure the welfare of migrant workers, the government, businesses, and civil society organisations must all play a critical role. The issues created by invisibility in the context of migration must be addressed by strengthening labour laws, implementing efficient monitoring measures, and providing information and support. Dr M. V. Bijulal argued throughout his presentation for institutional and governmental agencies to work together synergistically to address the issues migrant workers confront. He emphasised the requirement for thorough and organised thematic documentation of the many situations faced by migrants, such as their access

to healthcare, rationing, and labour rights. These aspects are now inadequately documented, which makes migrant labour invisible to the system.

The mistreatment of migrant workers on job sites and a lack of accountability in the data collection are two main problems contributing to invisibility. Many migrant workers are still unregistered or have incomplete documentation, which prevents them from being beneficiaries in government programmes and welfare services. Their difficulties are exacerbated by this marginalisation, which also prevents them from receiving crucial services and support.

Dr Bijulal emphasised that the responsibility towards migrant workers lies with the government, institutions, and society at large. The low-key approach towards social and civil responsibilities hampers efforts to address the issues faced by migrant workers effectively. He suggested adopting a rights-based development framework to counter this, drawing from the U.N. Human Rights Council's principles. Such a framework would recognise the denial of rights faced by migrant workers because of development activities that heavily rely on labour.

Highlighting the significance of migrant workers' contributions to development, Dr Bijulal urged for their inclusion in discussions around development agendas. By incorporating the concerns of migrant workers into development dialogues, policymakers can design more inclusive and sustainable strategies that protect workers' rights and welfare. To improve the visibility and recognition of migrant workers, Dr Bijulal proposed establishing a comprehensive documentation system that captures their living and working conditions. This data-driven approach would provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by migrant workers and facilitate the development of targeted policies and interventions.

Moreover, strengthening accountability mechanisms in worksites and data management can help ensure that migrant workers are not left invisible and excluded from government welfare schemes. Transparent data tracking and reporting are essential to address exploitation issues and effectively protect workers' rights.

Group Discussions

Dr Anjali Borhade and Dr Bijulal M. V. gave informative opening remarks to the first session, focused on the lives of migrants and project outcomes, respectively. Dr Anjali Borhade emphasised the forces that push and pull people to migrate, highlighting the importance of lower wages, unemployment, and higher minimum wages. She underlined the value of comprehending the social and health difficulties migrating

populations experience and divided migration into three categories: individual, family, and group migration. Dr MV Bijulal spoke about the project's results while addressing the lack of visibility surrounding migrant difficulties and the requirement for improved effort coordination. It was suggested that thematic documentation be used to understand better and manage migratory concerns. He also included the details of the ongoing SERB project's fieldwork and operations.

Following the presentations, delegates introduced themselves, representing government departments such as labour, health, and NGOs. Each representative shared insights into their department's approach to migrant issues.

- The health department delegate raised concerns about drug usage among migrants, which was linked to higher rates of diseases. Additionally, a delegate from Paippad Gram Panchayath highlighted the quick addiction to drugs among migrants due to homesickness and loneliness.

- Another delegate from Kanjirappally Panchayath mentioned the **lack of updated data on migrants**, especially during COVID-19. The limited information about migrants' whereabouts indicated a need for increased intervention by the Panchayath to address migrant welfare effectively.

- The retired supply officer discussed the low rate of Aadhar updating among enrolled migrants, impacting the "one card-one ration" scheme. Furthermore, the District Labour Officer explained the implementation of acts related to migrant workers and the common reasons for migration. The officer also brought up the issue of funding for expenses for transporting the corpses of deceased migrant workers.

The session concluded with a detailed account of the migrant situation in Kottayam district. There are approximately 34,000 enrolled migrant workers, and the Apna Ghar scheme has not been implemented in the district yet.

IN THE 2ND SESSION, THE DELEGATES WERE SPLIT INTO TWO GROUPS, EACH OF WHICH EXPLORED A TOPIC AND ITS SOLUTION.

Group 1

The prevalence of drug use among migrant workers is the main issue raised by the first group. Several migrant labourers have been discovered to be drug product carriers, suggesting they may be involved in drug-related activities. Additionally, the situation is made worse by people's ignorance of the effects of drug use. The group of migrant workers has seen an increase in violent occurrences because of drug addiction's effects.

To address these issues effectively, the following suggestions were put forward by the participants:

1. **Implementation of counselling services:** Providing counselling and support programs tailored to the needs of migrant workers can help address the underlying causes of drug usage and addiction, fostering a healthier and more informed community.

2. **Regular health check-ups:** Conducting periodic health check-ups for migrant workers can help identify early signs of drug use and addiction, enabling timely intervention and support.

3. **Registration at the Local Self-Government Department (LSGD) level:** Instituting a registration system for migrant workers with the LSGD can help

monitor their movements and activities more closely, facilitating better oversight and assistance when needed.

4. **Involvement of trade unions:** Trade unions can play a vital role in raising awareness about drug-related issues among migrant workers. By providing

instruction and support, trade unions can help educate workers about the risks of drug usage and advocate for healthier alternatives.

By implementing these measures, the first group aims to address the pressing problem of drug usage among migrant workers and create a safer and more informed environment for the entire community.

Group II

The second group found the reluctance of Migrant Workers to Enrol in the Aawaz Insurance Scheme. Several reasons contribute to the unwillingness of migrant workers to enrol in the Aawaz insurance scheme:

1. **Operational Challenges:** Migrant workers often face overcrowded living conditions in camps, making it difficult to find a suitable time to enrol in the scheme. Their work schedules might clash with enrolment timings, creating logistical problems.
2. **Lack of Sufficient Facilities:** Inadequate facilities and resources at enrolment centres may discourage migrant workers from participating in the Aawaz

insurance scheme. Limited infrastructure and long waiting times can deter them from completing the registration process.

3. **Floating Population of Migrant Workers:** Migrant workers frequently move from one place to another in search of employment opportunities. This transient nature of their work can make it challenging for them to register and stay enrolled consistently.
4. **Perceived Benefits:** Some migrant workers might have reservations about the perceived benefits of the AAWAZ insurance scheme. They may need to fully understand its advantages or believe the coverage is insufficient for their needs.

Solutions that they found regarding this issue were.

1. **Registration through Local Self-Government Departments (LSGDs):** Simplifying the enrolment process and allowing registration through LSGDs in various localities can make it more accessible for migrant workers, reducing the burden of crowded camps.
2. **Involvement of Akshaya and NGOs:** Employment agencies like Akshaya and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) can play a pivotal role in facilitating enrolment. They can help with registration, spread awareness, and assist workers in understanding the benefits of the Aawaz insurance scheme.
3. **Publicity and Awareness Campaigns:** The Aawaz insurance program's appeal among migrant workers can be increased by running focused public relations campaigns highlighting its benefits. It will be easier for them to grasp and encourage enrolment if the advantages and coverage are explained clearly.

The Kerala Government can encourage more migrant workers to participate in the Aawaz insurance programme, assuring their welfare and defending their interests by resolving these problems and implementing solutions.

During the brainstorming sessions, participants identified key areas for action, including:

- **Awareness campaigns:** launching focused awareness programmes to inform migrants of their rights, the welfare programmes they are eligible for, and the channels for requesting assistance in the event of infractions.
- **Skill development:** Enhancing programmes for migrant labourers' skill development to increase their employability may result in improved employment chances and higher salaries.
- **Accessible grievance redressal:** Creating direct as accessible channels for migrants to report instances of exploitation or prejudice this will ensure that their complaints are promptly addressed.
- **Community integration:** Promoting community integration programmes that give workers a sense of belonging and lessen the chance of prejudice.
- **Collaboration with employers:** Collaborating with businesses and deelopmet sectors to provide a setting that respects migrants' rights and guarantees their treatment relatively at work.
- **Capacity building of panchayats to prepare an action plan for migrant workers, as per GR of Kerala state government.**

This part of the workshop emphasized the value of forming partnerships with governments at all levels.

Workshop Outcomes:

Participants realised how crucial it was to form strategic partnerships with governmental organisations, local governments, and other stakeholders to gather the necessary resources and support for the action plan's effective implementation. The training program's emphasis on collaboration is designed to increase the ability of government representatives and civil society organisations in Kerala's Kottayam District, Kerala to build a long-lasting support system for migrant workers. The initiative intends to successfully solve the critical housing, education, legal assistance, health, and livelihood concerns that migrant workers in the area experience, by developing strong collaborations. The initiative further emphasized on the importance and need of multi-sectoral approach with active involvement and coordination among various departments such as urban development, health, women and child development, and skill development to work in co-ordination with Labour department. These departments can play specific role to provide their respective services to migrants irrespective of their migration status to sharpen focus on migrants in Kerala in the existing Kerala migrant welfare board.

The training workshop strongly advantages Kottayam's responsibility to lead by example among Kerala's districts in upgrading the lives of migrant workers and providing them with safe accommodation.

By fostering collaboration and facilitating knowledge exchange, we can pave the way for a more inclusive society that values the contributions and well-being of all its members. The journey towards achieving this goal will require continued engagement, deliberation, and policy design, but the groundwork has been laid for a brighter future.

Recommendation and Suggestion:

1. It is imperative to conduct a comprehensive study of panchayat-wise actual thematic census based descriptions of migrant workers in the Kottayam district, regarding living conditions, work patterns, participation in health and safety schemes, and the possibilities of ward-wise formation of residential cards. Kerala Government and Civil Society should provide financial assistance and advice for the study to be conducted jointly by Health, Labour, Local Self-Government Department, Public Administration programme at SIRP, Mahatma Gandhi University each associate with this development.
2. Labor Department of Kerala should focus on more awareness campaigns and targeted inclusion of migrant workers in Awaz- health insurance scheme. This should be done by entrusting an external agency to spread awareness and enrol migrant workers for the insurance scheme.
3. An action plan needs to be developed to facilitate advocacy and support from health and other concerned government department for improved access of services for health and social protection mainly livelihood -skilling and job support, legal support and financial inclusion of migrants. This can be led by health and labour department jointly collaborating and working on providing respective services to migrants irrespective of their migration status.
4. Government should discuss integrating the activities of the Disha Foundation and CMPIG collaboration with the Labor Department of Kerala. Kottayam district should be selected as the phase activity of "Shramgaurav" mobile app

activities in Kerala. The public administration department should set aside funds for building such a mobile application.

5. "Migrant Friendly Cell" should be formed in every Panchayat to alleviate the cultural difficulties faced by the migrant workers, regularly intervene in health problems, and monitor the labour workplace. In this, Mahatma Gandhi University and District Collectorate should be given the supervision responsibility of the cell. The cell should included Panchayat representatives, standing committee members, interested people from the public, educational workers and departmental representatives.
6. Online registration of contractors, migrant workers and employers is lightly desirable. Presently verification of this is vested in the Labor Department, which creates delays in sorting the data. Therefore, the government should take measures to sort the registration information in respective panchayats. Regular camps should be organised in panchayats to check and validate the information obtained through internship candidates. The responsibility of final approval of the information provided by each Panchayat should be given to the distinguished authority in the panchayat or District Labor Department.
7. The contractors should submit the details of workers working under a contractor or employer to the Panchayat. The Panchayat should ensure that the said migrant worker is registered. These workers should be called directly and informed by the Labor Department after ensuring the information provided is correct. The Labor Department should ascertain whether these workers are entitled to ESI and P.F. benefits and issue instructions to the contractor/ employer.
8. A "labour contract" must be issued by the state labour department, detailing where an immigrant will work, what work will be done, the work schedule, how long the work will be, and what benefits will be received from the job. Every migrant worker should know his rights through this document in various languages. M G University must develop a model contract.

9. Panchayat wise respective PHC / FHC should organise periodic medical camps for migrant women. Instead of just malaria and disease detection camps, a comprehensive camp by different health departments should be organised monthly. A representative of the Labor Department should be made responsible for this. Mobile health care units must be started as well.
10. Legal Aid Cell should be set up by public administration in Kottayam district. A special wing for migrant workers should be established in the Legal Aid Cell, which will operate on a 24x7 basis. Special training should be conducted in the Child and Welfare Department for women's safety. The Child and Women Welfare Department should conduct counselling to build confidence among migrant workers and their families.
11. The public administration should order clubs and reading rooms in respective districts to conduct awareness classes for migrant workers once a month. Libraries and reading rooms should provide opportunities for migrant students to work in the cultural sector and enhance their artistic skills.
12. More capacity-building workshops should be conducted for the government officials under the leadership of the district administration with the inclusion of CSR funds, and faculty members of academic institutions should be appointed as consultants.
13. A select group should make the all-programme schedule for collaborative action to include impact assessment of persons, respectively, academia, administration, and civil society.
14. The Kerala migrant welfare board should work in establishing institutional mechanisms for inter-state coordination and data sharing specially with source states' Labour and Tribal department- Madhya Pradesh, Jharkhand, Odisha, Bihar, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh.
15. There is a need to devise special strategies of information, education and communication (IEC) in the local languages of migrants to avail the existing services for them in Kerala, since majority of migrant workers are not familiar with local language in Kerala.

